

WASTE4THINK

Moving towards life cycle thinking by integrating advanced waste management systems.

What would happen if citizen and companies were aware of the waste they generate, the impact of this on the environment and the human health and the management costs?

MAIN OBJECTIVE

The main objective of Waste4Think is to move forward the current waste management practices into a circular economy motto demonstrating the value of integrating and validating 20 eco-innovative solutions that cover all the waste value chain. The benefits of these solutions will be enhanced by a holistic waste data management methodology, and will be demonstrated in 4 complementary urban areas in Europe.

The consortium in charge of carrying out the initiative is made up of a total of 19 partners from SMEs, public agencies and universities from 7 European countries.

